

SITE GS/SPHINX	DATE 6/27/79	AREA NE	SQUARE N3/W1	PAGE
 Feature No.	Coordinates:		Levels	
			Top: 10.59 ^{SW} CORNER 10.64 ^{SE} CORNER	Bottom: 10.44 SW Corner
	DIMENSIONS			
Diameter:	Width: ≈ 50 cm	Length: 70 + cm	Depth: 16 cm	

Locus	Mat.	Color	Hard.	Consis.	Pottery	Inclusions		
①	Gypsum	Tan - yellowish	Very Hard Packed	Fine Rubbly	T	Lm Frags ✓	Gp	
					O	Gr	Char Flecks ✓	
						Do		
						Ba		
D	Al							
	Other							
	②	Gypsum Limestone Sand Mix (prob. same as ①)	white - light buff	Hard Packed	Rubbly	T	Lm ✓	Gp
						O	Gr ✓ 1-2 small frags 1-2 mm	Char ✓ Charcoal Spots ✓
Do								
Ba								
D	Al							
	Other	Few minute frags corroded Copper						
	○					T	Lm	Gp
						O	Gr	Char
Do								
Ba								
D	Al							
	Other							
	○					T	Lm	Gp
						O	Gr	Char
Do								
Ba								
D	Al							
	Other							
	○					T	Lm	Gp
						O	Gr	Char
Do								
Ba								
D	Al							
	Other							

PHOTOGRAPH	Color: Roll/ C2 No./ 4,5	B&W: Roll/ 2 No./ 3,4
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DRAWN	Area Plan: 1:20 Plan	Feature Plan:	Sections: 2 sections
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REMARKS; INTERPRETATION: Notable none of granite dust or in FHS immediately at SE corner Fc17. SL Cable cuts across Fc17. So excavated sections NE, & SW corners. Bedrock bottom reddened (by scorching?)
 FHS actually in Fc17 gradient
 6 x 4.5 x 2
 Largest Limestone Frag. Range to very small